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ABSTRACTS

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**Plant mediated synthesis of CuO-ZnO bimetallic nanocomposite using
Theobroma cacao plant leaves**

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Abstract: Nanoparticles have unique chemical and physical properties. The green synthesis of nanoparticles provides several potential uses in the environmental and biomedical domains because it generates fewer toxic substances. This work describes the biosynthesis of CuO-ZnO (copper oxide-zinc oxide) bimetallic nanocomposite utilising leaf extract from *Theobroma cacao*, along with its characterization and potential application screening. Phytochemicals play reducing and capping roles in the CuO-ZnO bimetallic nanocomposite synthesis. The highest absorbance at 365 nm suggested the production of a bimetallic nanocomposite. The green synthesis of the bimetallic nanocomposite has been confirmed through initial analysis using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. FTIR was used to identify functional groups that were involved in the creation of bimetallic nanocomposite. The largest peak on the XRD graph, located at 36.21°, revealed the bimetallic nanocomposite crystalline structure. The mean dimension of the nanocomposite was found to be 14.82 nm. The Zn, Cu, and O peaks in the elemental composition seen in the SEM with EDS provide proof that the CuO-ZnO bimetallic nanocomposite was synthesized. DLS research revealed that the CuO-ZnO bimetallic nanocomposite had a hydrodynamic diameter of 94.7 nm. The surface charge of the particle was measured using the zeta potential, and the result was -46.9 mV, suggesting that bimetallic nanocomposite is more stable. The antibacterial capabilities of CuO-ZnO bimetallic nanocomposite are demonstrated.

Keywords: Greensynthesis, capping agent, CuO-ZnO bimetallic nanocomposites, antibacterial activity.

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